

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

№10

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

2025

oktyabr

Milliy nashrlar

OAK: <https://oak.uz/pages/4802>

05.00.00 – Texnika fanlari
08.00.00 – Iqtisodiyot fanlar

Google Scholar

OPEN ACCESS

ULRICHSWEB™
GLOBAL SERIALS DIRECTORY

Academic Resource Index
ResearchBib

ISSN INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CYBERLENINKA

OpenAIRE

ROAD

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

BASE

Crossref

НАУЧНАЯ ЭЛЕКТРОННАЯ
БИБЛИОТЕКА
LIBRARY.RU

РЭУ.РФ
РОССИЙСКИЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ
ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Elektron nashr, 741 sahifa.
2025-yil, 30-oktyabr,

Bosh muharrir:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, DSc, professor

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Shakarov Zafar G'afrovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, PhD, dotsent

Tahrir hay'ati:

Abduraxmanov Kalendar Xodjayevich, O'z FA akademigi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shaumarov Said Sanatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Turayev Bahodir Xatamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Allayeva Gulchexra Jalgasovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Arabov Nurali Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Maxmudov Odiljon Xolmirzayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Xamrayeva Sayyora Nasimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bobonazarova Jamila Xolmurodovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Irmatova Aziza Baxromovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bo'taboyev Muhammadjon To'ychiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shamshiyeva Nargizaxon Nosirxuja kizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor,

Xolmuxamedov Muhsinjon Murodullayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Xodjayeva Nodiraxon Abdurashidovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Amanov Otabek Amankulovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Zikriyoyev Aziz Sadulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sxay Lana Aleksandrovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Ismoilova Gulnora Fayzullayevna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Djumaniyazov Umrbek Ilxamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, dotsent

Ashurzoda Luiza Muxtarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Botirali Roxataliyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor

Tursunov Ulug'bek Sativoldiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Bauyetdinov Majit Janizaqovich, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti dotsenti, PhD

Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li, Texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sultonov Shavkatjon Abdullayevich, Kimyo fanlari doktori, (DSc)

Jo'raeva Malohat Muhammadovna, filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor.

muhandislik & iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil 28-avgustdagi 360/5-son qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

1. Toshkent shahridagi G.V.Plexanov nomidagi Rossiya iqtisodiyot universiteti
2. Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti
3. Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti" milliy tadqiqot universiteti
4. Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
5. Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
6. Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
7. Toshkent arxitektura-qurilish universiteti
8. Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
9. Jizzax politexnika instituti

MUNDARIJA

JAHON MOLIYA TIZIMIDA “YASHIL” MOLIYALASHTIRISHNI RIVOJLANISHINING MUAMMOLARI VA SHARTLARI	12
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	
EKOLOGIK MIGRANTSIYANI MINTAQAVIY MIQYOSDA MUVOFIQLASHTIRISHNING ASOSIY YO‘NALISHLARI	18
Bahtiyor Ismoilov Ulug‘bek o‘g‘li, Kadirova Zulayxo Abduxalimovna	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA BANK XIZMATLARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH HOLATI	25
Davletova Nilufar Tulanovna	
EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISHDA MINTAQANI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIGA TA‘SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI	30
Qodirov Farrux Ergash o‘g‘li	
SUV RESURSLARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING XORIY TAJRIBASI	37
Kadirxodjayeva Nilufar Raxmatullayevna	
MAHALLIY XOMASHYO BAZASIDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI ISHLAB CHIQARISH XARAJATLARINI KAMAYTIRISH YO‘LLARI	46
Sultanov Dilshod Normamatovich	
IQTISODIYOTI RIVOJLANGAN DAVLATLARDA INSON KAPITALIGA INVESTITSİYALARNI JALB QILISHNING O‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	50
Akhmadaliyeva Nikholakhon	
O‘QITUVCHILAR VA TALABALAR UCHUN INNOVATSION TA‘LIM DASTURLARINI ISHLAB CHIQISHDA XALQARO STANDARTLARGA MOSLASHUV MEXANIZMLARI	62
Yuldashev Iskandar Bahromovich	
YER QA‘RIDAN FOYDALANGANLIK UCHUN SOLIQLARNING ILMIY-TADQIQOTLAR SHARHI	68
Zoxidov Ismatjon Yunusjon o‘g‘li	
RESPUBLIKA IQTISODIY TARAQQIYOTIDA OLIY TA‘LIMNI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH VA INVESTITSIYA JOZIBADORLIGINING O‘RNI	74
Jonuzokov Mirzabek Kulmamatovich	
DAVLAT IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI MUSTAHKAMLASHDA SIYOSIY INSTITUTLARNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH STRATEGIYALARI	80
O. Nurmuradov	
ICHKI AUDIT SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH MEZONLARI VA BUXGALTERIYA MA‘LUMOTLARINING ICHKI AUDIT JARAYONIDA EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	85
Xamidov Javoxir Shavkat o‘g‘li, Muxitdinov Shoxijaxon Xudoyor o‘g‘li	
XORIJIY INVESTITSİYALARNI JALB ETISHNING MOLIYAVIY MEXANIZMLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	90
Xuramov Zafar Rajabaliyevich	
KORPORATIV TUZILMALARDA INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIKNI TA‘MINLASHNING AHOLI DAROMADLARINI OSHIRISHDAGI ROLI	95
Qurbonov Javlonbek Jurabekovich, Raxmatov Faxriddin Xasanovich	
GLOBAL RIVOJLANISH JARAYONIDA SUG‘URTA XIZMATLARINI ISLOH QILISH MASALALARI	99
Xushmuradov Oman, Ismoilov Sherzod Ismoil o‘g‘li	

DORIVOR O'SIMLIKLARNI QAYTA ISHLASHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	103
Usmonov Mirg'ulom Xoshim o'g'li	
BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHGA ERISHISHDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT TIZIMLARINI QO'LLASH METODOLOGIYASINING AHAMIYATI	109
Nasrulloev Hayotjon Xabibulloevich	
НЕЙРОИНТУИТИВНЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ КАК ФАКТОР КОНКУРЕНТНОГО ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА НА РЫНКЕ ТРУДА.....	115
Ягудин Дмитрий Рустамович	
RESURSLARNI SOLIQQA TORTISHGA OID TADQIQOTLARNING NAZARIY TAHLILI.....	123
Nasimdjanoov Yunusjon Zoxidovich	
SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILAR FAOLIYATINI MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH: XULQ-ATVOR IQTISODIYOTI VA PROGRESSIV TARIFLARNI LOYIHALASH	129
Abduraimova Nigora Abdugapparovna	
DAVLAT RAQAMLI LOYIHALARI: UZINFOCOMNING TA'LIM TIZIMI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKKA QO'SHGAN HISSASI	134
Raxmatxo'jayev Axrorxo'ja Akmal o'g'li	
РОЛЬ ЦИФРОВЫХ ПАСПОРТОВ В ПРОМЫШЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ И ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ.....	140
Мансурова Сайёра Бахтияровна	
BANK XIZMATLARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	148
Xolikova Oydin Olimjonovna	
PNEVMOMEXANIK YIGIRISH TEXNOLOGIYASI XUSUSIYATLARI	153
Jumaniyazov Kadam, Salimov Shuhrat Halimovich, Nazarov Ramazon Anvarovich	
GREEN INDUSTRY AND THE ECONOMY OF ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY CONSTRUCTION: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND UZBEKISTAN'S OPPORTUNITIES.....	158
Mansurova Sayyora Bakhtiyor kizi	
TELEKOMMUNIKATSIYA SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH TAHLILI	166
Suyunov Asror Baxtiyorovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA LOGISTIKA XIZMATLARINING MIKRO VA MAKRO TUZILMALARI, ULARNING FUNKSIONAL METADOLOGIK TAMOYILLARI.....	171
Z.Teshayev	
O'ZBEKISTONDA DAVLAT ULUSHI MAVJUD KORXONALARNI BOSHQARISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBADAN FOYDALANISH IMKONIYATLARI	176
Ismailov Allayor Rashidovich	
MAHSULOT TANNARXINI ANIQLASHDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH XARJATLARINI OG'ISHISHLARI VA ULARNI TAQSIMLASH	183
Raxmatov Baxriddin Baxtiyor o'g'li	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ СТОИМОСТИ СПОРТИВНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЙ И ОБЪЕКТОВ НА ОСНОВЕ АУТСОРСИНГА	186
Исмагулова Гульмира Нуралиевна	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYASI.....	193
Xaitov Oxunjon Nomoz o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANING INSTITUTSIONAL VA TASHKILYIY MEXANIZMLARI.....	198
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA UZOQ MUDDATLI RESURSLARNI JALB QILISHDA XALQARO TAJRIBA.....	203
Abduraxmonov Akmal Nurmatov o'g'li	

MEHNATGA LAYOQATLI TRANSPORT SOHASIDAGI AHOLINI ISH O'RINLARI BILAN TA'MINLANGANLIK HOLATINI TAHLILI	207
Abdullayeva Nigora Shamsiddinovna	
TO'QIMACHILIK SOHASINI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISH MODELI	212
Mdraximova Gulasal Ro'zimboy qizi	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT PORTFELI DIVERSIFIKATSIIYASI VA GAROV TA'MINOTI SIFATINING BANK BARQARORLIGIGA TA'SIRI	220
Xolbozorov Husniddin Norbek o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON - 2030 STRATEGIYASI DOIRASIDA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI BOSHQARISH: MUAMMOLAR VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	226
Norova Nozima Nabiyevna	
UY-JOY KOMMUNAL XIZMATLARNI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISHNING KLASTERLI MEXANIZMI TAHLILI	232
Odamboyev Oybek Ravshanbek o'g'li	
KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV TUZILMALARIDA MOLIYAVIY MUNOSABATLARNING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI	236
Qurbaniyazov Shaxzodbek Karimovich	
XALQARO SAVDONING RIVOJLANISHI VA ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALARI	242
Jalolov Bekzod Sherzod o'g'li	
TA'LIM TIZIMINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING YANGI TIZIMINI JORIY ETISHGA QARATILGAN NAZARIY JIHATLAR	247
Dusanov Salim Mamarasulovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BUDJET TUSHUMLARINI OSHIRISHDA BOJXONA AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	254
Aktamov Akbarjon Aslan o'g'li	
DAVLAT TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA QURILISH XARAJATLARI HISOBINI YURITISH	262
Ostonokulov Azamat Abdugarimovich	
РАЗРАБОТКА ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННЫХ МОДЕЛЕЙ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ КРЕАТИВНЫХ ИНДУСТРИЙ В ТУРИСТИЧЕСКУЮ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРУ РЕСПУБЛИКИ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН	273
Хошимова Камилла Навфал қизи	
A NEW STAGE IN THE APPLICATION OF MARKET MECHANISMS TO ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY	285
Ibrayim Maxkamov	
RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH ORQALI SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH XIZMATLARINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH USULLARI	291
Eshbekova Xayriniso Baxtiyorovna	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATI IQTISODIYOTIDA DXSH ASOSIDA INVESTITSIYA MUHITINING SHAKLLANISHI	297
Hamroyev G'ayratjon Sultonovich	
TURIZM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA MIJOZLAR EHTIYOJLARINI O'RGANISH VA TAHLIL QILISH	301
Shaymanov To'liqin Mahmayusupovich	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И ЦИФРОВЫХ ПОДХОДОВ В НАЛОГОВОМ ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬСТВЕ	306
Элбаева Мукаддас Рашидовна	
СИНТЕЗ НЕЧЕТКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕПЛОЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИХ ОБЪЕКТОВ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ	311
Бахриева Хуршида Аскарходжаевна, Сафаров Шохрух Шарофович, Бахрамов Муҳаммадали Ералиевичасистент	
ШАНХАЙСКАЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА КАК КАТАЛИЗАТОР ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКИХ ЦЕЛЕЙ РАЗВИТИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	319
Базарова Гулнара Гуламовна	

O'ZBEKISTON KORXONALARINING TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA BANK KREDITLASH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	323
Pulatova Moxira Baxtiyorovna	
QUESTIONS ABOUT THE STUDY OF PERFORMANCE AND EFFICIENCY OF APPLICATION OF LOADING AND EXTRACTING EQUIPMENT	327
Azamat Umirzokov	
MATOLARNING HAVO O'TKAZUVCHANLIGI KORRELATSION TAHLILI	334
Ismailov Nurulla Tuychibayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI RISKLARINI SUG'URTALASHNING AFZALLIKLARI	339
Mamadjanov Shuxrat Jalolidinovich	
IKKI QATLAMLI ARALASH TOLA TARKIBLI TRIKOTAJ TO'QIMASINI OLIISH USULI	343
Usnatdinova Elmira Faxratdinovna, Mirusmanov Baxtiyor, Abdurahimova Fazilat Abdullayevna	
MAHALLIY DAVLAT HOKIMIYATI ORGANLARIDA ENG ILG'OR TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA QAROR QABUL QILISH JARAYONLARINING OPTIMALLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	347
Axmedov Farxod Raxmonjonovich	
IMPACT OF FOREIGN INVESTMENTS ON THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN: CROSS-SECTORAL ANALYSIS	354
Jumayeva Kamola Azimjonovna, Khasanova Iroda Azizbek kizi	
KORXONA INVESTITSION FAOLLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING NAZARIY-USLUBIY MASALALARI XUSUSIDA	362
Ilyasova Barno Axmadovna	
MILLIY IQTISODIYOTGA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNI O'ZLASHTIRISHNING AMALDAGI HOLATI TAHLILI	371
G'afurov Sherzod Abduvaxob o'g'li	
EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH ASOSIDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	378
Raximov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHNI TA'MINLASHDA EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	385
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
SANOAT KORXONALARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY KONSEPTUAL MEKANIZMLARI	392
Jalolov Abbasxon Ravshanxon o'g'li	
TEPKI UZELI KONSTRUKTIV XOSSALARI TAHLILI	398
Bozorova Farida Maxmudjonovna	
НЕОБХОДИМОСТЬ ОБЪЕДИНЕНИЯ АКЦИЗНОГО НАЛОГА НА НЕФТЕПРОДУКТЫ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	405
Пулатов Дилшод Хақбердиевич, Маматкулов Салимжон Рахмонкулович, Хужамурадов Аброрбек Рўзимурат ўғли, Воронин Сергей Александрович, Абдиев Мансур Мусурмонович	
OLIY TA'LIMGA INVESTITSIYA SIYOSATI: IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA ISTIQBOLLAR	410
Talapova Nargiza Baxriddinovna	
INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE NETWORK	416
Bahriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTON INVESTITSION MUHIT VA UNGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI	421
Tirkashev Farruxjon Xolyigitovich	
МНОГОМЕРНАЯ БЕДНОСТЬ И УСТОЙЧИВОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ: ОЦЕНКА ЧЕРЕЗ РАМКУ МРІ	426
Мамаризоев Жахонгир Исохонович	
ОЦЕНКА И ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ВЛИЯНИЯ МАКРОЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ НА ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ СТАБИЛЬНОСТИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО ОБМЕННОГО КУРСА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	430
Норбаева Мухлиса Акрам кизи	

RAQAMLI TO'LOVLAR ASOSLARI VA XAVFSIZLIGI	440
Yaqubov Azizbek G'anibekovich	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA LOGISTIKA XIZMATLARINI BOSHQARISHNING INNOVATSION USULLARI	444
Xomidov Xojjakbar Adxamovich	
SOLIQ SIYOSATI ORQALI INKLYUZIV IQTISODIY O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH MEXANIZMLARI.....	449
Saydakbarova Madinaxon Anisbekovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA STARTAP EKOTIZIMINING SHAKLLANISHI VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHI YO'LLARI.....	454
Suleymanova Shoira Alavxanovna	
MILLIY IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNING O'RNI	459
Alimova Dilfuzaxon Rustam qizi	
MEHNAT BOZORINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISHNING MAKROIQTISODIY BARQARORLIKKA TA'SIRI.....	464
Botirova Sarvinoz Bobir qizi	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVNI TASHKIY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	469
Qurboniyazov Shaxzodbek Karimovich	
INVESTITSIYA FAOLIYATINI MUQOBIL MOLIYALASHTIRISH USULLARINING MANBALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH YO'LLARI	474
Boboqulov Akmal Muborakbekovich	
RAQAMLI MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINING MOHIYATI VA TURLARI.....	482
Zufarov Akmal Gulamiddinovich	
FISKAL BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SOLIQQA TORTISHNING TARTIBGA SOLISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	491
Sulaymonov Farrux Shuxratovich	
ИНДЕКС ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ МОНИТОРИНГА УРОВНЯ ЖИЗНИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ.....	496
Хазраткулова Лола Нармуминовна	
BANK MAJBURIYATLARI VA AKTIVLARINING VAQTINCHALIK NOMUTANOSIBLIK LARI RISKINI KAMAYTIRISH	502
Ibrohimov D.M.	
O'ZBEKISTON RAQAMLI PLATFORMALARI FAOLIYATIDA RAQOBAT SIYOSATINING ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI.....	507
Saparov Islom O'Imasovich	
RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI OSHIRISHDA MARKETING YONDASHUVLARINING QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIGA TATBIQI.....	514
Abdikarimova Zilola Baxramovna	
TIJORAT BANKLARI KAPITALI TARKIBIDA DAROMAD MANBALARINING ULUSHI VA KAPITALLASHUV JARAYONIDAGI O'RNI	520
Tursunov Mustafo Mirzayevich	
AHOLINI IJTIMOY HIMOYA QILISH TIZIMIDA INSTITUSIONAL HAMKORLIKNING O'ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI TAHLILI	524
Abdullayeva Sayyora Aleksandrovna	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK TIZIMIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI	528
Bobojonova Sevara Baxrombek qizi	
MINTAQA SANOATI RAQAMLI XIZMATLAR BOZORIDA TIJORATLASHTIRISHNI "SMART" MODELI	533
Norov Murodjon Maxmudovich	

TOMORQADAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH- KAMBAG'ALLIK MUAMMOSINI YUMSHATISHNING MUHIM OMILI	539
Xamidjon Shaxobov	
SUG'URTA KORXONALARIDA REZERVLAR HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	544
Najimova Nigora	
TO'QIMACHILIK MAHSULOTLARI EKSPORTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XITOIY BOZORINING O'RNINI	549
Mardanov Aziz Yusupovich	
THE IMPORTANCE OF GREEN ENERGY IN THE ECONOMY OF FERGANA REGION: CURRENT TRENDS AND PROBLEMS	555
Khayrullaev Zoidjon	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA MUAMMOLI KREDITLARNING UNDIRILISHI BO'YICHA XORIJ TAJRIBASI	559
Mitillayev Ibrohimjon Tursunpulatovich	
RAQAMLI MOLIVAVIY XIZMATLAR SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	563
Muyassarzoda Fayziyeva	
MOLIVAVIY MEXANIZM SIFATIDA SUG'URTA TASHKILOTLARI TO'LOVGA LAYOQATLILIGINI BELGILASHNING O'ZIGA XOS HUSUSIYATLARI	570
Abdullayev Erkinjon A'zamovich	
MAMLAKAT YAIM QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT HAJMINI STATISTIK VA EKONOMETRIK TAHLIL USULLARI ASOSIDA PROGNOZLASH	578
Jalolov Ilhomjon Isomiddinovich	
XALQARO TURIZM XIZMATLARI BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	585
Eshtaev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, Ivatov Irisbeg	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBI VA AUDIT TIZIMLARINI AVTOMATLASHTIRISHNING METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	590
To'laganov Ziyovuddin Kamolitdin o'g'li	
JAHON SEMENT SANOATIDAGI TENDENSIYALAR VA O'ZBEKISTONNING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	595
Abdujabbarov Abdulaziz Abdurashid o'g'li	
РОЛЬ ФИНАНСОВОГО АНАЛИЗА В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ.....	600
Бекбаева Феруза Бахтиеровна	
BARQAROR MOLIVAVIY RENTABELLIK BANKLARNING DAROMADLILIGINI TA'MINLASH OMILI SIFATIDA.....	606
Umarov Davron Shavkatovich	
REKLAMA XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKKA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR.....	612
Xamrakulov Azamat Baxritdinovich	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОБУЧЕНИЕМ (LMS) В ОНЛАЙН ОБРАЗОВАНИИ И ЕЕ РОЛЬ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ: АНАЛИЗ И СРАВНЕНИЕ	618
Атабоева Шахризода Равшановна, Бекчанов Бекчан Юлдашевич	
ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИЯ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА: ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ И НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ	623
Киличева Ф.Б.	
DAVLAT TIBBIYOT MUASSASALARIDA DEBITORLAR VA KREDITORLAR HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	628
Sultonova Mushtariy Abdulabbosovna	
NARX BELGILASH-IQTISODIY MANFAATDORLIKNING ASOSIY OMILI VA NARXNI SHAKLLANTIRISH TAMOIYILLARI	635
Soxadaliyev Abdurashid Mamadaliyevich	

SUTNI QAYTA ISHLASH KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDAGI ISHLAB CHIQRISH JARAYONLARINI TAHLIL QILISH.....	639
Normuradov Nurbek Sunatilloevich	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA BUDJET TUSHUMLARINI OSHIRISHDA TARIF STAVKALARINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH ORQALI FISKAL BARQARORLIKNI KUCHAYTIRISH (OZIQ-OVQAT IMPORTI MISOLIDA).....	644
Rizayev Mirmahmud Xotamjanovich	
IPOTEKA KREDITLASH JARAYONINING XORIY TAJRIBASI.....	652
Akrom Mardiyev	
O‘ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARI MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGI TAHLILI	659
Ulashbayev Shohruh Abdivaxobovich	
CHARACTERISTICS OF APPLYING NEW HETEROCOMPOSITE POLYMER MATERIALS IN ENGINEERING ACTIVITIES	665
Umida Ziyamukhamedova, Mirjalol Abdulakimov	
ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ «МАХАЛЛАБАЙ»: ДЕЦЕНТРАЛИЗАЦИЯ И ТЕОРИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ.....	672
Қосимжонов Нозимжон Қозимжон ўғли	
EKOLOGIK AUDITNI TASHKIL ETISHDA RISKLARNI JORIY ETISH TARTIBI	676
Abdullayev Xurshidjon Nazrullo o‘g‘li	
CORPORATE CULTURE AND ITS ROLE IN TALENT MANAGEMENT	683
Shoyunusova Arofat, Sanjar Mirzaliev	
SIRDARYO VILOYATI SHAROITIDA BIOMASSA ASOSIDA OZUQA ISHLAB CHIQRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	687
Xazratkulov Niyoz Namazbayevich	
ПУТИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОГО МЕХАНИЗМА В УСЛОВИЯХ РЫНОЧНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	692
Воронин Сергей Александрович, Азимова Феруза Маликовна	
ENERGETIKA LOYIHALARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISHDA TO‘SIQLAR VA IMKONIYATLAR	700
Tilakov Ismoiljon Usmonovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA SOG‘LIQNI SAQLASH TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	706
O‘roqov Firdavs Ortiqniyoz o‘g‘li	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI BOZORLARNI MONOPOLIYAGA QARSHI TARTIBGA SOLISH MEKANIZMLARI VA TAKOMLLASHTIRISH TAKLIFLARI.....	710
Mingboev Asqar Qandaharovich	
JAHON SEMENT SANOATIDAGI TENDENSIYALAR VA O‘ZBEKISTONNING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	717
Abdujabbarov Alisher Abdullayevich	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO‘LLARI	722
Mufitillayeva Safiya Qodir qizi	
KORXONALAR FAOLIYATINI BAHOLASHDA STATISTIK AXBOROT TIZIMINING O‘RNI	728
Musurmonova Mahbuba Omonovna	
INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR VA ULARNING AGRAR SOHAGA TA‘SIRI.....	732
Ortiqov Sulton Davronqul o‘g‘li	
DIRECTIONS FOR EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING OF COSTS.....	736
Pardaeva Shakhnoza Abdinabiyevna	

DIRECTIONS FOR EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING OF COSTS

Pardaeva Shakhnoza Abdinabiyevna

Associate Professor of Tashkent State

University of Economics, DSc

Email: shahnoza.pardayeva.94@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0002-0654-8152

Abstract. The article identifies the problems of strategic management accounting of costs, traditionally formed and used in practice, and justifies the need to develop new and effective mechanisms for managing and accounting for costs at enterprises. Based on this conclusion, it is shown that currently, in world practice, three priority areas for organizing and conducting strategic management accounting of costs, income, and financial results are applied.

Keywords: cost, value chain, strategic management accounting of costs.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada an'anaviy tarzda shakllanib, amaliyotda qo'llanilayotgan xarajatlarning strategik boshqaruv hisobi bilan bog'liq muammolar aniqlanib, korxonalarda xarajatlarni boshqarish va hisobga olishning yangi hamda samarali mexanizmlarini ishlab chiqish zarurligi asoslab berilgan. Shu xulosaga asoslanib, hozirgi vaqtda jahon amaliyotida xarajatlar, daromadlar va moliyaviy natijalarni strategik boshqaruv hisobini tashkil etish va yuritishning uchta ustuvor yo'nalishi qo'llanilayotgani ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: xarajat, qiymat zanjiri, xarajatlarning strategik boshqaruv hisobi.

Аннотация. В статье выявлены проблемы стратегического управленческого учета затрат, традиционно формирующиеся и используемые на практике, и обоснована необходимость разработки новых и эффективных механизмов управления и учета затрат на предприятиях. На основе этого сделан вывод, что в настоящее время в мировой практике применяются три приоритетных направления организации и ведения стратегического управленческого учета затрат, доходов и финансовых результатов.

Ключевые слова: затраты, цепочка ценности, стратегический управленческий учет затрат.

INTRODUCTION

The problem of managing and accounting for costs is a complex and important process that encompasses the entire operational process of any enterprise. At a time when the modernization of the economy is underway, deep structural changes are being carried out in all sectors of the economy of our country, in our opinion, the following factors that determine the essence of this problem are clearly evident: when managing and accounting for the costs of enterprises, a number of important external factors that affect their formation are not taken into account at all or their impact is not paid enough attention; the effectiveness of the current system of providing information for the process of making important strategic management decisions related to the activities of the enterprise is not noticeable or in such cases it is clearly seen that it is completely useless; the information provided by accounting systems that traditionally perform the function of information presentation is in most cases almost useless, delayed or inaccurate, which has led to a sharp decrease in their effectiveness. The traditionally formulated and practically applied management accounting has the following problems: from the point of view of management accounting, the incorrect classification of costs into conditionally variable and conditionally fixed groups; incorrect formation of cost prices in times of sharp increase in the volume of enterprise activity, which is not related to the volume of production; ineffectiveness of methods used to allocate indirect (secondary, curved, etc.) costs; inability to make strategic management decisions based on available data; ineffectiveness of the normative method of cost accounting used to determine the cost price of a unit of manufactured product. This situation, in itself, requires the development of new and effective mechanisms for managing and accounting for costs in enterprises.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the digital economy, the main goal of all business entities is to obtain high profits. Of course, achieving this result is closely related to a number of processes. The most important of them is the recognition of income and expenses. In business entities, expenses, like income are also the main indicators of financial performance [1].

Local economists N.B.Abdusalamova, U.U.Kostaev, A.Kh.Pardaev, B.A.Khasanov, A.A.Kashimov have researched the main indicators of financial results, including the theoretical and methodological aspects of expenses [2].

Also, in the scientific research works of A.Kh.Pardaev and U.U.Kostaev, the functions of the categories of income and profit received by economic entities, the correlation between the increase in income and profit growth in economic entities and the deviations in the ratio between the changes in these indicators relative to costs were analyzed [3]. CIS economists V.B.Ishavkevich, V.E.Kerimov, I.G.Kondratova, V.F.Pali also paid special attention to the organization of strategic management accounting in economic entities on the basis of costs, further improvement of calculation methods used in strategic management accounting of costs and budgeting issues [1, 5]. A.Z. Avlokhlov, one of the economists of our country, based on the results of his scientific research, showed the methodological and methodological differences between the categories of "cost", "expenditure" and "expense" from the cost indicators representing financial results [6]. As noted by N.B. Abdusalamova, "...the peculiarity of cost center planning and accounting is that the costs are considered to be the correct costs for him. Thus, the curved costs are slightly reduced and the share of the correct costs in the product cost increases" [4]. A.K. Ibragimov, B.A. Khasanov, N.K. Rizaev proposed new technologies and innovative approaches aimed at organizing and maintaining cost management accounting in business entities [7]. Tashnazarov S.N. proposed the forms of the "Report on profit and loss and other comprehensive income", "Report on the cost of products (work, services)" and an improved methodological procedure for applying the variable costing system in the preparation of these reports [8, 9].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article used methods such as grouping data based on specific facts, analyzing social and economic situations based on studying their structure, analyzing and synthesizing them and comparing statistical data, taking into account the index and normative methods.

Analysis and discussion of results

The results of scientific research show that currently in world practice, three priority areas of organizing and conducting strategic management accounting of costs and financial results are used:

1. By the directions of enterprise activity through the formation of the value chain (M. Porter);
2. Based on the growth of costs during product movement (B. Ryan);
3. Through strategic cost management (Dj. Shank and V. Govindaradjan).

In doing so, the organization of strategic cost management accounting is based on the following important principles:

- use of strategic cost management mechanisms;
- formation of a value chain in the directions of enterprise activity;
- formation of information on the growth of costs during the movement of products;
- using the principle of tracking the entire product movement to make decisions.

The concept of value chain formation was developed by M. Porter, based on the principle of dividing the activities of enterprises into main and auxiliary groups.

The formation of a value chain is a set of coordinated actions by each enterprise from the production of a product to meeting the requirements of its final consumer, that is, it is understood as a direct accounting of all processes, starting with the process of concluding contracts with suppliers of raw materials and ending with the delivery of the manufactured product to the final consumer. Each link in the chain forming the value chain should feel responsible for delivering a quality product to the next link in the chain, minimizing costs and ensuring that the final product is competitive. Using M. Porter's value chain in strategic management accounting - creates the opportunity to clearly distinguish separate areas of activity of enterprises, take into account both internal and external costs in these areas and effectively manage them.

It is necessary to form the necessary information for the purpose of strategic cost management not only on the general activity, but also on the cost types of the cost amount in each activity. Admittedly, the existing methods of cost grouping are not in the interests of strategic management accounting. In order to effectively organize and maintain strategic management accounting, the following grouping method is proposed, which differs from the approach of grouping costs used in practice for the benefit of management accounting (Table 1):

As is known, for the purpose of organizing and maintaining management accounting, expenses are primarily classified into conditionally variable and conditionally permanent groups.

At the present time, when globalization, modernization of the country's economy, attracting foreign investments and expanding the geography of exports are on the agenda, we believe that such a division of costs into fixed and variable groups is not appropriate. Currently, many economists and practitioners consider variable costs to be unprofitable from a strategic perspective. More precisely, if we proceed from the goal of strategic development, we believe that it would be more profitable to consider all costs as variable. From this point of view, it is appropriate to divide costs into a series of avoidable, increasing and fixed costs in terms of their consideration when making strategic management decisions.

Table 1. Grouping of expenses in the account of strategic management

№	Grouping icon	Expense type
1.	Depending on their participation in strategic decision-making	0.1. Unavoidable expenses; 0.2. Eliminated expenses; 0.3. Rising costs.
2.	Depending on the time of appearance	2.1. Past period expenses; 2.2. Current period expenses; 2.3. Future period costs.
3.	Depending on the level of management	3.1. Managed costs; 3.2. Unmanageable costs.
4.	Depending on the type of activity	4.1. Basic expenses; 4.2. Ancillary costs.
5.	Depending on the participation in the movement of the product	5.1. Basic resource costs; 5.2. Auxiliary resource costs.
6.	Depending on the position in the cost of the manufactured product	6.1. Costs that create added value; 6.2. Costs that do not add value.
7.	Depending on the consideration of strategic decision-making	7.1. Relevant expenses; 7.2. Irrelevant expenses.

Unavoidable costs are realized regardless of any strategic management decision made by the management of the enterprise, that is, their amount does not change.

At the same time, the amount of costs eliminated will change based on the strategic management decisions made. In the process of organizing strategic cost management accounting, we believe that it is necessary to pay attention to the growing cost category and to separate such costs into a separate classification group and take them into account. Because all material, financial and labor resources associated with the production process, as well as the costs of infrastructure, technological processes and product design, can be kept at the same level. In this case, the total amount of costs does not change over a certain period of time. If strategic management decisions are made to improve, update or invest in certain aspects of this direction, the amount of such costs will increase and these two situations will bring different effects to the business entity. The classification of expenses into expense groups based on the time of their occurrence - past, current and future - is carried out in order to determine the time of their occurrence, since this approach makes it possible to correctly calculate the amount of income for a certain period and accurately calculate the amount of final financial results. Grouping cost data in strategic management accounting in the above-proposed methods creates the basis for the systematic formation of cost data for each enterprise's areas of activity, ensuring their efficiency, rational use of resources and the correct formation of the final result. Organization of strategic cost management accounting in enterprises based on the principle of grouping that we propose requires the following actions (algorithm of actions): the main and auxiliary activities in the value chain of the enterprise are separated and analyzed; the center of cost groups is determined for each separately allocated activity; items (elements) that make up costs for each line of activity are determined; distribution of costs by types of manufactured products is carried out; the cost of a separate product unit is determined; the final financial result is formed.

The results of the above-mentioned actions in order to organize strategic cost management accounting necessarily require the introduction of new positions in the chart of accounts. Based on the above proposals and scientific conclusions, we propose to open a number of additional sub-accounts to the current "Main Production" account in order to organize strategic cost management accounting at enterprises, in particular: "Enterprise infrastructure management costs"; "Labor resource management costs"; "Material and technical support costs"; "Costs of creating new product types and assortments"; "Costs of searching for and creating

new technologies”; “Costs of delivering products to the consumer”; “Costs of providing services for the sale of products”.

The proposed sub-accounts will allow for the formation of accounting data by type of expenses in the main and auxiliary activities at the level of each enterprise. Also, in order to form an effective basis for cost analysis, we consider it appropriate to divide them into the following components, in accordance with the proposals of the Russian scientist E.V.Isayeva (Table 2).

Table 2. Formation of account information on the lines of activity of the enterprise

Areas of activity	Used account position (sub accounts)	The source from which information is formed
Main activity	“Primary production costs”; “Material and technical support costs”; “Costs of product delivery to the consumer”; “Product realization service costs”	Basic production cost estimate, Estimate of preparation and supply costs, Realization estimate Service cost estimate
Auxiliary activity	“Costs of managing the enterprise’s infrastructure”; “Costs of managing labor resources”; “Costs of material and technical support”; “Costs of creating new product types and assortments”; “Costs of searching for and creating new technologies”.	Infrastructure Estimate Resource Cost Estimate

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The formation of a value chain, that is, a comprehensive accounting of the costs incurred from the time a substance in the form of raw materials passes through several stages until it reaches the consumer in the form of a finished product:

- determining the logical chain of product creation;
- choosing the most optimal option for product movement based on objective data formed on the costs of each stage of technological processes;
- to determine the main, secondary, important and non-important costs that add value to the product;
- accounting and management of all stages of purchasing raw materials from buyers, manufacturing products from them, and delivering finished products to consumers, as well as the impact of internal and external factors on these stages and the costs associated with them;
- in order to effectively organize the strategic management of expenses in enterprises, it creates the opportunity to divide the directions of their activities into the main and auxiliary directions.

List of used literature

1. Pardayev A.X., Pardayeva Z.A. Boshqaruv hisobi: Darslik /T.: “Iqtisod-Moliya”, 2019. -556 b.
2. Paradaeva Sh.A. Xo’jalik subyektlarida moliyaviy natijalarning strategik boshqaruv hisobini takomillashtirish. “Xalqaro moliya va hisob” ilmiy-elektron jurnal. www.interfinance.uz, №3, 2021 yil, iyun.
3. Abdinabi Kh. Paradaev, Umidjon U. Kostaev. The improvement of organizing strategic management accounting, Journal of Critical Reviews, 7(18), c. 718-721, ISSN-2394-5125 vol. 7, ISSUE 18, 2020.
4. Abdusalomova N.B. Xarajatlarni kelib chiqish joylari va javobgarlik markazlari bo’yicha xarajatlarni boshqaruv hisobini tashkil qilish. “Xalqaro moliya va hisob” ilmiy-elektron jurnal. www.interfinance.uz, №1, 2016 yil sentyabr.
5. Керимов В.Э. Стратегический учет. Учебное пособие / В.Э. Керимов – М.: Омега-Л, 2005. 168 с.
6. Avloqulov A.Z. Moliyaviy natijalar hisobi va auditi metodologiyasini takomillashtirish. /Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc) dissertatsiyasi avtoreferati. - Toshkent, 2019 yil.
7. Amaliy boshqaruv hisobi. Oliy o’quv yurtlari uchun o’quv qo’llanma. /A.K. Ibragimov, B.A. Xasanov, N.K. Rizaev. – T.: “Moliya”, 2014. – 404 b., 187-197 betlar.
8. Tashnazarov S.N. Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida moliyaviy hisobotning nazariy va metodologik asoslarini takomillashtirish. /Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc) dissertatsiyasi avtoreferati. - Toshkent, 2019 yil, 73 bet.
9. Tashnazarov S. The main ways of the improvement of financial reports in the Republic of Uzbekistan (about balance sheet and the report of financial results). //Journal of Manajement Value & Ethica. ISSN: 2249-9512, Vol. 6, Oct-Dec. 16, - №4. P.109-119. GIFO.565

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. № 10

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

+998 93 718 40 07

<https://muhandislik-iqtisodiyot.uz/index.php/journal>

t.me/yait_2100